

THE NEED TO IMPROVE THE VICTIMOLOGICAL PREVENTION SYSTEM IN ENSURING THE STABILITY OF THE SOCIO-MORAL ENVIRONMENT IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society, victimological prevention and its dialectical features in ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society, and the prospects for improving the victimological prevention system in ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment. Modern conceptual approaches and views on ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society are also analyzed.

Key words: society, socio-spiritual environment, social laws, victimological prevention, traditionalism and modernity, comparative analysis, analysis and synthesis, systemic and functional, dialectical nature, stability.

INTRODUCTION. The Department of Public Safety, in particular, the prevention (senior) inspectors of the mahalla law enforcement agency, in their activities on victimological prevention of offenses, implement a system of legal, social, organizational and other measures of general, special, individual victimological prevention of offenses in order to identify and keep track of victims of administrative and criminal offenses and persons prone to victimization, identify and eliminate the causes of victimization and the conditions that enable them. In this regard, they implement joint general measures aimed at early identification, elimination, neutralization of victimological factors and reducing their impact, as well as calling on persons with a high level of victimization to be vigilant, reducing their level of victimization, and reducing the risk of them becoming victims of criminal and any other forms of aggression. It is noteworthy that in the victimological prevention of crimes, we must not forget that the activities to implement these measures are focused not on the person who is prone to committing crimes, but on those who are prone to being victims of crimes and on eliminating the factors that form such a tendency in them.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS. Theoretical and methodological foundations of ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in

society, victimological prevention and its dialectical features in ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society, the origin of cases of violence against minors and child victimization, issues related to the importance of ensuring the rights of the child in international law T.V. Varchuk, E.N. Yershova, L.S. Alekseyeva, B. Neil, A.L. Genley, B. Fortson, J. Klevens, M. Merrick, L. Gilbert, S. Alexander, S. Graham, S. Limber, P. Olvis, L.V. Frank, D.V. Rivman, Y.M. Antonyan, V.S. Ustinov, I.A. Fargiyev, V.I. Polubinsky, Q.R. Abdurasulova, I.U. Ismailov, J.S. Mukhtorov, S.B. Khojakulov, Analyzed in the scientific works of scientists such as D.R. Turayeva, Sh.K. Giyasov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. As many countries in the world as there are, there are vices such as crime, delinquency, corruption that have a direct negative impact on the positive changes of the country, and this requires constantly identifying their causes, finding ways to eliminate them, and combating them. It should be noted that in our country, maintaining public order and ensuring security, preventing crimes and combating crime are urgent tasks, and this is the main task of the internal affairs bodies.

Our wise people did not say for nothing that a house where there is a quarrel for one day will not be blessed for forty days. For this reason, after the head of our state, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, began his activities as President, the fight against crime and the prevention of offenses have risen to the level of state policy in our country. Significant work is being done in our society to ensure the important principles of “Law and justice are a priority” and “Punishment for crime is inevitable”, to improve the activities of the court, prosecutor's office, internal affairs bodies, and the bar, and to literally turn them into defenders of human rights and interests.

As our President noted, the most important task of those responsible is to identify a crime, find its cause, prevent offenses, and curb it. It is better to prevent a crime than to punish a criminal. It is necessary to strengthen cooperation in this direction. The fight against crime should be a criterion for the activities of not only law enforcement agencies, but also all of us. Strengthening public control is also of great importance in preventing crime. Also, a person cannot be educated only by punishment, only by repressive methods. Life itself has proven this many times. To educate a person, the whole society must act, and first of all, we must eliminate the causes and factors that create criminal situations from our lives.

The Strategy of Actions on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 provides for such tasks as “increasing the

effectiveness of coordination of activities in combating crime and preventing offenses". This requires the introduction of advanced practices, working methods and innovative technologies into the activities of internal affairs bodies in our republic, improving their activities in legal, organizational, methodological, material and technical terms and providing them with qualified personnel, maintaining public order and ensuring security, and preventing offenses on the basis of increasing the effectiveness of the participation of public structures.

Over the past period, large-scale reforms in this area have been implemented and are being implemented in our republic. In particular, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention", "On Internal Affairs Bodies", the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", dated April 10, 2017 No. PF-5005 "On measures to radically increase the efficiency of the activities of internal affairs bodies, strengthen their responsibility in ensuring public order, reliable protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens", dated March 26, 2021 No. PF-6196 "On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies to a qualitatively new level in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime", and the "Organizational Regulation on Further Improving the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies" dated April 12, 2017 "On measures" No. PQ-2883, "On measures to radically improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of maintaining public order and ensuring public safety" No. PQ-2940 dated May 1, 2017, "On the introduction of a qualitatively new system of maintaining public order, preventing offenses and combating crime in the city of Tashkent" No. PQ-3528 dated February 14, 2018, "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of maintaining public order, preventing offenses and combating crime in the city of Tashkent" No. PQ-3786 dated June 19, 2018, "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of ensuring public order, preventing offenses and combating crime in the city of Tashkent" No. PQ-4075 dated December 24, 2018, Resolution No. PQ-5050 of April 2, 2021 "On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime" and other regulatory and legal documents of the ministry in this area set out the tasks that must be performed in the field of maintaining public order and ensuring safety, and preventing crimes.

Based on the above-mentioned laws and by-laws, the system is studying the

experiences of foreign countries in combating crime and preventing crimes, and introducing advanced innovative technologies.

As society is always developing, crime is also developing, becoming more complex and improved. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the activities of all law enforcement agencies, in addition to the internal affairs bodies that are currently engaged in the prevention of crimes and the detection of crimes.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime to a qualitatively new level” stipulated that local law enforcement agencies should be gradually established on the basis of the bases of internal affairs bodies, that the local law enforcement agency should be considered the main link in ensuring public safety in the region, preventing crimes and combating crime, that the relevant sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies in the region, as well as the National Guard and other state bodies, should be organized on the basis of the local law enforcement agency, and that the preventive inspector should be entrusted with the task of systematically organizing and coordinating the work of ensuring public safety, preventing crimes and combating crime by the local law enforcement agency.

Based on these tasks, on November 29 of this year, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Approval of the Concept of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Measures for Its Implementation” was adopted. This decree developed the strategy “Development of the Public Security System in the Republic of Uzbekistan” for 2022-2025.

The main tasks of the strategy were to regulate, systematize relations in the field of public safety, eliminate existing legal gaps and conflicts, maintain public order, prevent crimes, ensure road safety, and coordinate probation activities, including developing and constantly improving an algorithm for the joint movement of forces and means of ministries and departments involved in holding public events, widely introducing modern forms and methods of work and advanced information technologies into public safety activities, minimizing the human factor in service activities by increasing the digitalization of the public safety system to 90 percent, and sharply reducing recidivism by persons under preventive accounting, administrative control, and probation control.

CONCLUSION. As part of the large-scale reforms being implemented in our country, special attention is being paid to ensuring a peaceful and quiet life for the population and the formation of a culture of law-abidingness and public safety in our society. In particular, completely new mechanisms and procedures

for organizing work in the field of ensuring public safety on the basis of the principle of "Serving the interests of the people" have been introduced, and purposeful cooperation between state bodies and public structures has been established. At the same time, the growing number of various dangers and conflicts in the world, threats to national peace and tranquility, pandemics, natural and man-made disasters impose on responsible state structures the task of further improving their activities based on the priority idea of "All efforts are for human dignity."

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